

Fabrication of SiC Fiber-Aluminum Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

Silicon carbide (SiC) fiber reinforced aluminum composites have been fabricated and some of the factors affecting the fabrication process were investigated. The SiC fiber manufactured from an organosilicon polymer was used in the present study. The fabrication technique using aluminum powder slurry and hot pressing was developed.

INTRODUCTION

The SiC fiber manufactured from an organosilicon polymer is continuous and flexible, and furthermore, has high tensile strength and excellent oxidation resistance (1) (2) (3). Those properties of the SiC fiber are well suited to the requirements for the reinforcement in metal matrix. The reinforcer in metal matrix should be compatible with the matrix material. The compatibility of the SiC fiber with aluminum has been investigated and reported that the SiC fiber was well compatible with solid aluminum and fairly compatible with liquid aluminum (4). Several techniques for fabricating the composite of fiber and metal matrix have been proposed, however, the method combining metal powder slurry and hot pressing was adopted in the present study.

The purpose of this investigation is to find the fabrication technique suitable for the SiC fiber-aluminum composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROEDURE

The coreless SiC fiber manufactured by the Nippon Carbon Co. Ltd. was used in the present study. The scanning electron micrographs of the SiC fiber are shown in Fig. 1. The mean diameter of the fiber was 14.6 μm , tensile strength, 2020 MPa and elastic modulus, 160 GPa as measured by the authors (5). The atomized aluminum powder of -200 mesh was used for making the slurry. The preliminary experiments showed that sodium alginate was most effective as a dispersion agent

for metal powder slurry. The slurry of aluminum powder was prepared by mixing aluminum powder of the volume fraction of 50 % with 0.5-1 % sodium alginate solution while agitating. A yarn of 500 SiC filaments was immersed into the slurry and pulled up continuously so that the yarn was impregnated with aluminum powder. The apparatus used for impregnating the yarn is schematically shown in Fig. 2. The impregnated yarn was dried, and then heated at temperatures from 600 to 900°C in an argon atmosphere by pulling up the yarn through a small furnace at the speeds of 1-20 cm/min. A kind of precursor was formed after this heat treatment. The precursors were cut into pieces and the pieces were stacked in a graphite die and hot pressed in vacuum using pressures of 5-50 MPa for 5-30 min at temperatures in the solid state, or in the liquid state of aluminum. For the comparison, some of the impregnated yarns were cut into pieces and directly hot pressed with the same conditions. The microstructures of the fabricated composites were examined by an optical microscope and also by a scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Silicon carbide fiber synthesized from an organosilicon polymer is continuous and flexible with a round section and a smooth surface, as shown in the scanning electron micrographs in Fig. 1. Furthermore, the fiber has high tensile strength, excellent oxidation resistance and low density. This SiC fiber is suitable for reinforcing fiber in metal matrix as well as graphite fibers. The SiC fiber-aluminum composites would have high potential for use in weight-saving structures, if the fiber can be incorporated into aluminum matrix.

Among the proposed fabrication techniques for metal matrix composites, the technique using metal powder slurry is considered to be advantageous for continuous processing. The application of the slurry method to the fabrication of SiC fiber-aluminum composite was once reported (6) (7). However, little has been reported on this method.

The dispersion agent for making slurry is an important factor in the slurry method. According to the preliminary experiments, sodium alginate was more effective for dispersing metal powder than the others; monomers and alcohols.

The following disadvantages are considerable in the slurry method.

- (1) The control of fiber fraction is difficult.
- (2) The crevices in the inside of the yarn can not be eliminated.
- (3) Slurry is apt to fall off on handling.

Two improvements were made to minimize these disadvantages in the present study. The one is the use of a nozzle attached to the apparatus for impregnation and the other is the addition of the preliminary heating of the impregnated yarn before hot pressing. The nozzle scrapes excess slurry from the yarn, crushes the crevices in the inside of the yarn and smoothen the surface of the yarn. Fig. 3 shows the cross-sections of the impregnated yarn after passing through the nozzle. It is shown that the inside of the yarn is filled with aluminum powder and no crevices are found in the yarn. The preliminary heating of the yarn was carried out in two temperature ranges; in the solid state and in the liquid state of aluminum. By the liquid state heating, increase in fiber fraction and elimination of the crevices in the yarn were achieved. However, the long time heating resulted in the degradation of fiber strength. By the solid state heating, bonding between powder particles was strengthened so that aluminum powder did not fall off. In this case, the long time heating is needed to get the strong bonding. Anyway, handling of the yarn becomes easier by the preliminary heating. The preferable conditions for the preliminary heating were as follows; temperature: 720°C, pulling up speed: 20 cm/min for liquid state heating and 650°C, 2 cm/min for solid state heating.

The precursors formed by the preliminary heating were hot pressed

using two temperature ranges; in the solid state and in the liquid state of aluminum. By the liquid state hot pressing, high density composite was achieved. However, the long time hot pressing resulted in the degradation of fiber strength as the case of preliminary heating. By the solid state hot pressing, stronger composite was achieved, but the long time hot pressing was needed to get stronger composite. The preferable conditions for hot pressing were; temperature: 700°C, pressure: 20 MPa, time: 5-10 min for the liquid hot pressing and 650°C, 50 MPa, 30 min for the solid state hot pressing. The satisfactory composites were obtained by the adequate combinations of the preliminary heating and hot pressing. The preferable combinations were; (1) solid state preliminary heating and liquid state hot pressing, (2) liquid state preliminary heating and liquid state hot pressing, (3) liquid state preliminary heating and solid state hot pressing. Fig. 4 shows the cross-sections of the composites fabricated by the combination of solid state preliminary heating and liquid state hot pressing. Thus, the composite with high fiber fraction can be easily achieved using this fabrication technique.

The composites fabricated by the direct hot pressing of the impregnated yarns were inferior to those hot pressed after preliminary heating.

CONCLUSIONS

The fabrication technique for SiC fiber-aluminum composite using the metal powder slurry and hot pressing was investigated and the following conclusions were obtained.

(1) Sodium alginate is well suitable for the dispersion agent for making aluminum powder slurry.

(2) A nozzle for scraping the excess slurry is usefull to produce the favorable yarn impregnated with aluminum powder.

(3) The preliminary heating of the impregnated yarn before hot pressing makes the handling of the yarn easy and is effective for fabricating the sound composite.

(4) The satisfactory composite can be achieved by the adequate combination of the preliminary heating and hot pressing, in the solid state or in the liquid state of aluminum.

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(a)

(b)

Fig. 1 Scanning electron micrographs of SiC fiber.
(a) cross-section, (b) surface.

Fig. 2 Apparatus for impregnating SiC yarn with aluminum powder.

Fig. 3 Cross-sections of impregnated SiC yarn.
 (a) longitudinal, (b) transversal.

Fig. 4 Cross-sections of fabricated SiC fiber-aluminum composite materials with various volume fraction of SiC fiber.
 (a) $V_f = 16.8\%$, (b) $V_f = 27.7\%$, (c) $V_f = 44.3\%$ and (d) $V_f = 51.6\%$.

